

Emergence of a new type of life and alive creature from mixing cells of plants and animals

Alireza Sepehri ¹ *

¹ *Research Institute of Astronomy-Astrophysics of Maragha (RIAAM), Iran.*

In this research, we show that by mixing cells of plants and animals, a new type of alive creature or life is emerged. To this aim, we cut the skin of some quails and create a hole between skin and skeleton. We put some some beans and lentils in this hole and cover it by a black glue. We open the hole after a week and observe that a bridge of quail's cells is produced between beans and lentils. This bridge has the genus of the periosteum that covers the outer surface of all bones. In this periosteum, there are some stem cells that produce a collection of neuronal circuits. These circuits could join to each other and form a little brain. This brain can control all voluntary and non-voluntary actions of this new alive creature.

Keywords: Alive creatur, Plant, Animal, Genetic Engineering

I. INTRODUCTION

One of main subject in science is producing new alive creatures by mixing cells of various types of life on the earth. However, there are some problems in producing these new types of creatures from connecting cells of animals and plants. For example, type of chromosomes of birds are different completely from type of chromosomes of mammals[1, 2]. In contrast to the XY sex-determination system in mammals, in the ZW system, the ovum determines the sex of the offspring. Males are the homogametic sex (ZZ), while females are the heterogametic sex (ZW). The Z chromosome is larger and has more genes, like the X chromosome in the XY system (See figure 1). This differences in chromosomes leads to the differences in radiation of waves by chromosomes. Previously, it has been shown that chromosomes act

* sepehri.science81214@gmail.com

like the receiver or sender of waves and have circuits similar to the radio [3]. Differences between chromosomes of birds and mammals lead to the emergence of two types of circuits and receiver or sender of waves. Consequently, the exchanged information between these two types of chromosomes are hard and connecting them seems to be impossible. This differences can be observed between chromosomes of birds and plants so [4, 5]. This leads to the differences in the production of two different receiver and sender of waves in cells of birds and plants. Consequently, the connection between cells of these two types of creatures is hard.

FIG. 1: Differences between chromosomes of mammals and birds

In this research, we will propose a method which connects cells of a type of bird with cells of two types of plants. We will show that body of a bird has this ability to produce a tissue which connects cells of animal and plant. This tissue is very similar to periosteum [6] and includes some stem cells. Some of these stem cells has the ability to produce neurons. These neurons join to each other and form neuronal circuits. A collection of these circuits can form a little brain. This little brain acts like a real brain and contributes in voluntary and non-voluntary action (For literature about little brain see [7, 8]). Thus, by connecting cells of birds and plants, some new creatures are produce that could be clever.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In section II, we will discuss the method for producing new alive creature. In section III, we will discuss about properties of this new type of creature.

II. THE METHOD FOR PRODUCTION OF NEW ALIVE CREATURE

In this research, we investigate a method for connecting cells of animals and plants. This connection is very hard because chromosomes of plants and animals are completely different. However, in some events, these two types of creatures could mix with each other and produce a new creature. In this research, we propose a method for producing this mixture.

We cut the skin of some quails with some special scissors and used of some ataractic drugs for killing pain. This causes that a hole is emerged between skin and skeleton of quails (See figure 2). We put some beans and lentils in this hole and covered it by a black glue (See figure 3). After a week, we removed glue and observed that a cellular tissue is formed between beans and lentils (See figure 4). We considered the genus of this tissue and found that it is very similar to the periosteum that covers the outer surface of bones (See figure 5).

FIG. 2: A quail with a cavity or hole between its skin and skeleton

III. PROPERTIES OF NEW TYPE OF CREATURE

In previous section, we proposed a method which produce a new creature from mixing cells of animals and plants. To this aim, we have used of cells of quails, beans and lentils. We observed that by puting plants in a hole between skin and skeleton of quails, a new tissue is emerged which acts like a bridge between cells of plants. This tissue is very similar to the periosteum that covers the outer surface of all bones. Also, this periosteum like bridge has some stem cells that able to produce neurons (See figure 6). If the process of the growth of

FIG. 3: Covering the cavity in quails body by black glue

FIG. 4: Picking up package of beans, lentils and cellular tissue which connect them

this new alive creature is continued, some neuronal circuits are emerged on this tissue which may be the initial stage of formation of a little brain. This little brain has the main role in voluntary and non-voluntary actions of this new creature. Maybe, this system becomes a clever creature and does some wonderful actions.

FIG. 5: Package of beans, lentils and cellular tissue which connect them

FIG. 6: Considering properties of new type of creature

IV. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

We made a hole or cavity in the body of some quails and put some beans and lentils in it. This hole was placed between skin and skeleton of quails. Then we covered this cavity or hole by a black glue. After a week, we removed glue and observed that a cellular tissue is formed between beans and lentils. This tissue is very similar to the periosteum that covers the outer surface of all bones. Also, some neuronal circuits were emerging on this tissue which may be the initial stage of formation of a little brain. This means that by putting plants in body of animals, a connection between cells of plant and animal is formed. This may produce some hopes for producing a new type of life and alive creature from mixing cells of plants and animals.

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